

DEVICE-EDGE-CLOUD INTELLIGENT COLLABORATION FRAMEWORK

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D3.2 Final Architecture And Interface

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Executive Summary

This deliverable provides an overview of the final architecture of the DECICE framework, including its interface and key components. The document gives a detailed explanation of each component, their functionality, and how they interact with each other. Additionally, the deliverable outlines the API specifications within the framework, providing guidance on how to access relevant documentation. The security measures implemented within the framework and Kubernetes are also discussed, with a focus on data storage, data transfer, and user management. This includes an examination of the protocols to ensure the secure deployment and integration of the framework with external services. Furthermore, this deliverable provides insight into the deployment process of the DECICE framework, highlighting the steps taken to ensure seamless integration with external services. The document also acknowledges the challenges encountered during the development process and presents a roadmap for future enhancements and improvements.

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1 Purpose and Scope of the Deliverable

The primary objective of this deliverable is to provide a comprehensive overview of the finalized architecture of the DECICE framework. Additionally, this document includes detailed explanations of the framework's API specification, related documentation, and implemented security measures. A summary of the framework's deployment is also provided. Furthermore, potential future enhancements to the framework are outlined.

2 Abstract / publishable summary

This deliverable presents the finalization of the DECICE framework's architecture and APIs, which have undergone significant improvements and refactoring since the previous deliverable, D3.1 - Synthetic Test Environment.

To ensure the secure transfer of critical data through the framework's layers, an OAuth2 authentication mechanism has been implemented, enhancing security, user access, and reliability. Furthermore, the combination of HTTPS, TLS 1.3, and Role-Based Access Control has been employed to secure data transfer. On the Kubernetes side, RBAC, TLS certification, and hierarchical namespaces have been implemented to facilitate secure communication between pods and prevent unauthorized access to user data. To facilitate easy deployment, the developed components have been containerized, and Helm Charts have been created for each component. Additionally, GitLab CI/CD pipelines have been utilized to manage the deployment process. The interoperable components of DECICE have enabled seamless integration with external services, such as Prometheus and Grafana. This deliverable also discusses the challenges encountered and outlines future steps, including planned enhancements such as a Software Development Kit (SDK) and web interface.

The primary outcome of this work is the finalization of the architecture, which enables easy enhancement of the framework in terms of development and deployment. This achievement provides a solid foundation for future development, allowing for more efficient and effective integration of new features.

3 Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to the achievement of all the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1.1 of the project plan:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable
(O1) Develop a solution that allows to leverage a compute continuum ranging from cloud and HPC to edge and IoT.	This deliverable provides an overview of the overall DECICE framework architecture, highlighting its efficient management of the hybrid compute continuum.
(O2) Develop a scheduler supporting dynamic load balancing for energy-efficient compute orchestration, improved use of green energy, and automated deployment.	This deliverable demonstrates the integration of the Integrated AI Scheduler with the Production Environment and the Virtual Training Environment (VTE).
(O3) Design and implement an API that increases control over network, computing and data resources.	This deliverable details the development and functionality of various APIs within the DECICE framework, providing insight into their operational mechanics.
(O4) Design and implement a Dynamic Digital Twin of the system with AI-based prediction capabilities as integral part of the solution.	This deliverable outlines the deployment processes for integrating developed components within the DECICE framework into the hybrid compute continuum.
(O5) Demonstrate the usability and benefits of the DECICE solution for real-life use cases.	This deliverable shows the DECICE framework's capabilities in providing a unified management layer for the hybrid compute continuum.
(O6) Design a solution that enables service deployment with a high level of trustworthiness and compliance with relevant security frameworks.	This deliverable describes the security measures and methodologies used within the DECICE framework itself, as well as those securing the hybrid compute continuum.

4 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

No significant changes to the project plan were made. No significant challenges were encountered during implementation.

5 Sustainability

Design and optimization of components in the project are tightly coupled to multiple WPs such as WP2, WP3 and WP4. Every partner in each work package will communicate their result regularly for an optimal integration of each component into the framework.

6 Dissemination, Engagement and Uptake of Results

6.1 Target audience

As indicated in the Description of the project, the audience for this deliverable is:

✓	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This report is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

6.2 Record of dissemination/engagement activities linked to this deliverable

See Table 1.

Type of dissemination and communication activities	Details	Date and location of the event	Type of audience activities	Zenodo Link	Estimated number of persons reached
None	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0

Table 1: Record of dissemination / engagement activities linked to this deliverable

6.3 Publications in preparation OR submitted

See Table 2.

In preparation or submitted?	Title	All authors	Title of the periodical or the series	Is/Will open access be provided to this publication?
None	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

Table 2: Publications related to this deliverable

6.4 Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

None.

7 Detailed report on the deliverable

This deliverable provides a comprehensive and systematic overview of the finalized architecture and interfaces for the DECICE framework. Since the publication of our last deliverable, significant progress has been made in refining the system's architecture and enhancing its capabilities. These advancements are detailed in the following sections, offering insights into how the system has evolved to address the technical and functional requirements of the project.

The first section begins with a discussion of the architectural refinements and progress achieved since the previous deliverable. This section highlights the most notable changes made to the DECICE system, focusing on improvements that have enhanced the overall design, functionality, and efficiency. The next section presents a thorough overview of the system architecture, providing a detailed breakdown of each component and microservice. It breaks down each component and microservice, explaining their specific roles and how they interact with one another within the framework and training environment to form a cohesive and efficient system architecture.

The subsequent section focuses on the API specification and documentation, detailing the user facing endpoints that facilitate interaction with the DECICE framework and training environment, as well as the internal routes that enable seamless communication between microservices. The section also discusses the use of the HTTP protocol to implement RESTful services, the adoption of OpenAPI for a thorough documentation, and the mechanisms in place for authentication and authorization to ensure secure and reliable user interactions.

The Integration and Interoperability section examines how the DECICE framework integrates with external services, including the compute plane for job submission and computation, as well as monitoring tools like Prometheus and Grafana. It also describes the deployment strategies employed, such as containerization and the use of Kubernetes for orchestrating the framework and compute plane.

Lastly, the report discusses the challenges encountered during development and outlines potential areas for future enhancement. While the architecture has been finalized, ongoing efforts will focus on improving usability, user-friendliness, accessibility, and security in upcoming development sprints.

7.1 Architectural Refinements and Progress

Since the initial architecture outlined in *D3.1 - Synthetic Test Environment*, significant changes and advancements in terms of architectural refinement have been made in the development of the DECICE framework in order to enhance development speed, scalability and security. One of the most notable advancements is the introduction of a central managing instance for both - the virtual training (VTE) as well as the production environment (PE). Since the design and development of the VTE began earlier than the production environment, the VTE was already in a beta state when the development of the actual DECICE framework began. In design workshops within work package 3 (WP3) we realized that the initial design of the VTE fits the requirements of the production environment quite well and only minor adaptations were needed to start the development process. In return, observations we did when writing the production instance led to significant improvements for the VTE which we had not yet put into consideration. This back and forth development cycle ultimately led to a unification of both instances. The VTE controller was encapsulated and refactored into the more general controlling instance *DECICE Control Manager (CM)* and also integrated in the production framework.

Both CMs now have the same capabilities in terms of user management, job scheduling, telemetry observation and security measures with only minor differences in route calling of different microservices. One example being the provision of a job or multiple jobs: while the PE allows for job uploading and scheduling on real systems in a heterogeneous compute plane, the VTE allows for

one or multiple historical jobs can be used to train the AI compute scheduler. Another example is the save and secure data upload of data that is used for computation. In response to these new functional requirements, we introduced additional services dedicated to data preprocessing and validation. These services ensure that data entering the system adheres to predefined standards, thereby improving the reliability of downstream processing. The incorporation of these components was driven by the need to handle an increasing variety of data sources and formats. While the VTE does not need to provide external data upload to another system, the PE needs to provide users with a function of data upload to the compute plane for further processing. We also undertook a comprehensive refactoring of the authentication and authorization mechanisms. The original system utilized a basic token-based authentication, which, while functional, did not offer the granularity required for complex user roles and permissions. We implemented a Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) system integrated with OAuth 2.0 protocols. This enhancement provides a more secure and flexible framework for managing user permissions, aligning with best practices in cybersecurity. To improve system maintainability and facilitate future development, we standardized the technology stack across all microservices. By adopting a uniform set of frameworks and libraries, we reduced compatibility issues and streamlined the development process. This was already discussed in D3.1 but is now finalized in D3.2. With these changes, for future features and refactoring only one component needs to be extended and the changes can automatically be reflected in the other.

7.2 Overview of System Architecture

For clarity on the DECICE's architectural layout and operational workflow, Figure 1 presents an overview, combining the framework's key components with a simplified control flow diagram that clarifies the scheduling decision-making process. This workflow consists of the following key steps:

1. The DECICE Control Manager decides that it is time to perform scheduling and triggers the process.
2. The DECICE Control Manager calls the PromQL-to-JSON Wrapper to refresh the metrics in the Digital Twin.
3. The PromQL-to-JSON Wrapper requests the latest metrics from the Metrics Storage via PromQL queries and converts them to JSON.
4. Then the PromQL-to-JSON Wrapper pushes these new metrics to the Digital Twin causing it to replace its previously held JSON data.
5. The DECICE Control Manager triggers the Scheduler Controller to perform scheduling decisions on the current data in the Digital Twin.
6. The Scheduler Controller accesses the Digital Twin to receive the current cluster state as JSON.
7. The Scheduler Controller calls the Prioritizer to create a scheduling queue from all jobs with pending pods, ordering them based on their priority, age and whether parts of them are already running.
8. The Scheduler Controller enters a loop to iterate over the queue of jobs and calls the Filter,

to determine the pool of eligible nodes based on policies and resource requests for each pod in the current job.

9. The Scheduler Controller sends the JSON data of the current job and the eligible nodes per pod to the Integrated AI Scheduler.
10. After the Integrated AI scheduler decides on Job/Node mapping, these scheduling decisions are sent to the DECICE Control Manager.
11. The DECICE Control Manager starts scheduling by forwarding this information to the Platform Specific Glue Code.
12. The Platform Specific Glue Code submits job specifications to the Kubernetes API on the Compute Plane.

Figure 1: DECICE production architecture

DECICE Control Manager

The CM serves as the central hub for the majority of the DECICE framework's business logic, as nearly all control flows are routed through it. The CM provides a set of endpoints and collaborates

with other components and services in the framework. It provides a set of internal APIs that are used for communication and information routing through the network as well as external facing APIs end users can interact with. These DECICE APIs (cf. D-APIs Section 7.3) have been implemented to give user the capabilities to securely and safely interact with and monitor the framework from an administrator point of view as well as to submit and track jobs for computation on the compute plane.

Platform Specific Glue Code

The Platform Specific Glue Code (PSGC) serves as a crucial intermediate component that enables the communication between the CM and the Kubernetes platform's API. This bidirectional interface allows the CM to issue control commands to the Kubernetes API, ensuring a control over cluster resources, as well as retrieve relevant data from the API, thereby providing the CM with valuable insights.

The PSGC is designed to interact with the Kubernetes API (KubeAPI), enabling the CM to orchestrate Kubernetes resources, including pods, deployments, and jobs, and gather valuable data from the KubeAPI. The integration process utilizes a standardized API call structure, ensuring ease of use and maintainability. Moreover, the PSGC integrates with the Kubernetes scheduler API to provide the transfer of scheduling decisions. Once received, these decisions are translated into the DECICE internal format by the PSGC for easy handling and execution.

The PSGC's modular design allows for potential future expansions to support other Kubernetes-related components or adjacent platforms, thereby further enhancing the DECICE system's versatility.

Compute Continuum

The compute continuum is a hybrid environment that includes High-Performance Computing (HPC), cloud, and edge devices to efficiently run user workloads. It is mainly built on existing open-source technologies for cluster management and scheduling, such as Warewulf¹ and Slurm² on the HPC side, and OpenStack³ on the cloud side, which are then integrated with the DECICE components in the control plane. At the heart of the compute plane is Kubernetes⁴, a powerful container orchestration platform that provides the fundamental building blocks for running containerized jobs across multiple physical systems. To extend its capabilities, Kubernetes is combined with KubeEdge⁵, an open-source system that enables the use and management of autonomous edge devices.

Digital Twin

The Digital Twin is a digital model that represents the current status of a computing system spread across a continuum of devices at the edge to cloud and high-performance computing (HPC) environments. This model serves as a "virtual replica" of the physical infrastructure, to support analysis and decision-making. One of the core purposes of the DECICE Digital Twin is to assist

¹Warewulf - <https://warewulf.org/>

²Slurm - <https://slurm.schedmd.com/documentation.html>

³OpenStack - <https://www.openstack.org/>

⁴Kubernetes - <https://kubernetes.io/>

⁵KubeEdge - <https://kubedge.io/>

the AI Scheduler in making informed, adaptive scheduling decisions. By providing real-time data on system performance, the Digital Twin enables the AI Scheduler to optimize job scheduling, improve energy efficiency, and respond to changing workload conditions across the continuum.

Scheduler Controller

The primary function of the scheduler controller is to compile and prepare data on two key sets: eligible nodes and pending jobs, utilizing real-time information coming from the Digital Twin. Its operation involves accessing the current cluster state from the Digital Twin and utilizing a Prioritizer to order jobs by priority, age, and running status. It then iterates through the queued jobs, filtering eligible nodes based on policies and resource requests. For each job, the Controller engages the Integrated AI Scheduler by converting job and node data into a compatible format and then receives scored scheduling decisions. After processing the entire queue, the controller updates node resources and sends all finalized scheduling decisions to the Control Manager.

Metric Storage (Prometheus)

Prometheus⁶ serves as the centralized metrics storage within the DECICE framework, collecting and storing a wide range of metrics from various sources. This includes Kubernetes job metrics, host energy metrics, CPU and memory utilization metrics, storage metrics, and more. By providing a unified repository for these metrics, Prometheus enables the Digital Twin and the Integrated AI Scheduler to access and leverage this data. The stored metrics are then used to optimize resource allocation and make scheduling decisions, ultimately contributing to improved efficiency, performance, and sustainability within the system.

PromQL-to-JSON Wrapper

The PromQL-to-JSON Wrapper component plays a crucial role in fetching the latest metrics from the Prometheus Metrics Storage by executing PromQL queries. It then converts these metrics into a JSON format, making them easily accessible and interpretable. Subsequently, the PromQL-to-JSON Wrapper pushes these new metrics to the Digital Twin, causing it to replace its previously held JSON data with the updated information. This periodic refresh of metrics is essential because the Integrated AI scheduler relies on this data to make informed and optimized scheduling decisions, ultimately leading to improved efficiency and performance.

Metric Dashboard (Grafana)

Grafana⁷ provides interactive and customizable metrics dashboards within the DECICE framework by retrieving metrics from the Prometheus Metric Storage. Authorized users can log in to the web-based interface and access these dashboards, which offer real-time visualizations and insights into the system's performance and behavior.

⁶Prometheus - <https://prometheus.io/>

⁷Grafana - <https://grafana.com/>

Integrated AI Scheduler

The Integrated AI-Scheduler is designed to dynamically optimize and manage job scheduling across diverse compute environments, including HPC, cloud, and edge systems. By incorporating a range of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) techniques, such as deep learning and reinforcement learning, the scheduler predicts and determines the optimal scheduling strategy based on the specific requirements of jobs and the characteristics of available nodes. Key advancements in the Integrated AI-Scheduler include:

- **Real-Time Scheduling Across Environments:** Development of an AI model capable of scheduling jobs in real-time across cloud, HPC, and edge environments, ensuring adaptability and responsiveness.
- **Efficient Strategy Retrieval:** Implementation of a caching mechanism that enables the efficient retrieval of job-node combinations and their corresponding best strategies, reducing latency and enhancing overall system performance.
- **Intelligent Resource Allocation:** Improvement in overall energy efficiency and job throughput through intelligent resource allocation, aligning with the goals of sustainable computing and high-productivity workflows.

Virtual Training Environment

The virtual training environment serves as a dynamic simulation platform where the scheduler is exposed to a variety of synthetically generated or real historic compute job scenarios. This allows us to iteratively refine our scheduling algorithms in a controlled, risk-free setting.

In the VTE, users initially log in to the DECICE web interface. From there, they have the flexibility to request a training in one of two ways: either by uploading their own custom data sets or by selecting predefined scenarios from ScenarioDB. Upon receiving this request, the VTE Controller redirects it to the Digital Twin. The Digital Twin, in turn, retrieves the requested data from ScenarioDB using a wrapper and then forwards the formatted data, again utilizing a wrapper, to the AI Scheduler for training. An overview of the VTE architecture is illustrated in Figure 2. Since the VTE follows CM in terms of architectural design and structure, both control and information flows are similar and do not differ besides a few interfaces that have been implemented differently. For instance the VTEs Control Manager is not capable of calling a compute plane and the Wrapper has an interface for doing database calls to a SQL DB instead of reaching out to a Prometheus instance.

7.3 API Specification and Documentation

In modern distributed and containerized software systems, API documentation is an essential and integral part for both users and developers alike. On one hand it serves as a tool on how to correctly and efficiently use the application without any major incidents and on the other hand it provides a baseline for developers to implement new features and tools to enrich the capabilities of the application. A well implemented documentation facilitates developer understanding and onboarding, ensures consistent implementation and improves maintainability and debugging. For the DECICE

Figure 2: DECICE virtual training environment

framework we have created a sophisticated documentation consisting of two parts - a technical documentation and a product documentation - which will be discussed in this section.

Technical Documentation

The first and foremost part of the documentation are the records of the overall architecture of the DECICE framework. It serves as an entry point for understanding the whole application and its capabilities. It was created during the design phase and is the foundation for building the system. The architectural documentation of the production and training system is depicted in Figure 1 and Figure 2. Due to the architectural design of the framework and modular development, each microservice also comes with its own documentation in the form of code documentation and API documentation, as well as database schemas for those services that are writing to or reading from a database. Code documentation is provided in the form of comments that are attached to each function. When using an appropriate code editor and language server the editor itself can provide code documentation when hovering over functions or function calls. The code documentation also gets exported externally by providing an HTML rendered output that can be viewed in a browser, allowing for hosting the documentation decoupled from the code base. The framework uses a tool called Sphinx⁸ that allows for an easy and automated creation of an external documentation that can even be automated in a CI/CD pipeline when new code is pushed, altering the documentation.

Since the framework is using a RESTful approach for exchanging information via HTTP we chose

⁸Sphinx - <https://www.sphinx-doc.org/en/master/>

OpenAPI⁹ for our documentation, a specification and standard for building, describing, and consuming RESTful APIs. Each service provides routes that can be called to retrieve, send or alter different information, depending on the capabilities and tasks of each service. These operations happen in the form of: GET, POST, UPDATE, DELETE that are being send between services. An example documentation is depicted in Figure 3. It shows an excerpt of the Control Managers routes for handling users, it allows for creating and deleting users as well as updating retrieving user information.

user		^
GET	/v1/user/me/	Get current user
PATCH	/v1/user/me/	Update current user
GET	/v1/user/	Get all users
PATCH	/v1/user/{id}	Update user
DELETE	/v1/user/{id}	Delete user by ID

Figure 3: DECICE Control Manager user handling

These routes are part of the broader API spectrum we implemented in the CM and are part of *Task T3.2: DECICE API*, the DECICE APIs (D-APIs). The D-APIs consist of four key APIs handling job and user specific tasks, telemetry tasks, security and the overall control mechanism of the scheduler and the platform as a whole.

- **Control & Security** (*Administrative API*): Enables administrators to manage users, configure settings, and issue commands to the underlying platform.
- **Login** (*Authentication Endpoint*): Accepts username and password combinations from users, returning a scoped token upon successful login. This process leverages OAuth2 workflows.
- **Job Management** (*Job Submission & Inquiry*): Allows authenticated users to submit new jobs or retrieve information about existing jobs, with submission permissions restricted to projects for which they have authorized access.
- **Telemetry** (*Metrics Access*): Provides users with telemetry data, filtered according to their permission levels. Metrics can be retrieved via existing API routes that execute PromQL queries on the backend or by directly submitting PromQL queries.

The OpenAPI documentation is useful for developers and users of an SDK alike. It not only provides insights into what routes to call to retrieve a specific information, it also specifically states how the request should like and provides an example upon a successful or bad request. An outlook of how the documentation looks like is further depicted in Appendix A.

Product Documentation

Besides the technical documentation of the DECICE framework and its functionalities there is also a product documentation available which we are also using internally as a team documentation. This has two benefits. It allows new developers to maneuver themselves through the development process more quickly and serves as a central point of entry to understand the usage of the system. It is

⁹OpenAPI Specification - <https://www.openapis.org/>

also the foundation for a proper product documentation once the applications launches to give end users the possibilities to quickly find their way through the framework. Figure Figure 4 depicts our current product documentation, the DECICE Knowledge Base.

Figure 4: DECICE Knowledge Base

It offers in-depth insights into the architectural documentation, JSON structures of the job submission process, DB schemas and dependencies necessary for a successful deployment of the whole application as well as tutorials for setting up and configuring dependencies for the compute plane such as Rook, Ceph or BeeGFS depending on the storage solution that will be picked. Properly written README files which are often used by users to get a first idea on how an application works when scrolling through GitHub or GitLab repositories are also placed in the repository, complementing the user documentation for the DECICE framework.

7.4 Security Measures

In this section, we detail the security measures implemented within the project. These measures are designed to ensure the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of data and resources. The discussion is divided into two key areas: the DECICE Framework, which represents the foundational aspects of the project's architecture, and Kubernetes, the container orchestration platform used to manage workloads and deployments securely.

7.4.1 DECICE Framework

Security measures are critical to ensure the trustworthiness, reliability, and resilience of the DECICE Framework and its operations. In an environment where sensitive data flows through multiple layers - spanning edge devices, cloud platforms, and containerized infrastructures - security safeguards are necessary to protect against unauthorized access, data breaches, and malicious attacks. Without robust security measures, the framework would be vulnerable to threats like data theft, service disruptions, and regulatory non-compliance, which could undermine stakeholder confidence and jeopardize project success. In the development process of the DECICE framework we focused on three critical areas: data transfer, data processing and data storage. Each of these components plays a vital role in ensuring the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of the system

Data Transfer

Securing data transfer is a critical aspect of safeguarding sensitive information as it moves across networks, especially in distributed and interconnected environments. However, several vulnerabilities can compromise the confidentiality, integrity, and authenticity of data in transit. These vulnerabilities include unencrypted transmission, which leaves data exposed to interception; weak protocols that fail to provide adequate protection against evolving cyber threats; insecure APIs that can be exploited to access or tamper with data during transfer; and inadequate endpoint verification, which may allow malicious actors to masquerade as legitimate systems.

These vulnerabilities expose data transfer to significant threats. Man-in-the-middle attacks can intercept and manipulate data in transit, replay attacks can use captured transmissions to gain unauthorized access, and eavesdropping can reveal sensitive information to attackers. Additionally, improperly secured data transfer can fall victim to traffic analysis, where even encrypted traffic is analyzed to infer sensitive details about the communication.

To mitigate these vulnerabilities and address potential threats, we have implemented a robust suite of security measures. All data transfers are secured using HTTPS and TLS 1.3, which provides strong encryption and eliminates outdated cryptographic vulnerabilities, making the communication between the user and the server running the DECICE framework secure. Additionally, an RBAC system integrated with OAuth 2.0 protocols is employed to ensure that only authenticated and authorized entities can initiate data transfers and access the platform, adding an extra layer of control. To fully use the platforms capabilities users need to register and setup an account first, providing a strong password during the registration process. To further enhance security, we deploy mutual authentication between endpoints, ensuring that all communication occurs only between verified parties. To ensure continuous protection and rapid response to anomalies, we have integrated extensive logging within the framework to be able to collect and display the logged information using the monitoring capabilities using Grafana. This system collects and visualizes real-time data on data transfer activities, providing detailed insights into the flow of information across the network.

Data Processing

Ensuring the security of data processing is critical, as this stage is vulnerable to several risks that can compromise the integrity and reliability of the system. Key vulnerabilities include untrusted code execution, where data processed with unverified scripts or third-party libraries could introduce malicious behavior, and insufficient input validation, which leaves the system open to injection attacks, such as SQL injection. Additionally, excessive permissions in processes that do not follow the principle of least privilege expose sensitive data unnecessarily, while resource exhaustion vulnerabilities allow attackers to overload system resources through malicious inputs, potentially leading to service disruption.

To mitigate these risks, we have implemented a robust set of best practices. All inputs are thoroughly validated and sanitized before processing, reducing the risk of injection attacks. Only trusted and verified libraries or scripts are used to ensure secure and authenticated code execution. We also used a set of ORM layers abstracting database reads and writes to prevent code injection that could enable attackers to execute arbitrary code during processing, potentially accessing or modifying

sensitive data. To enhance isolation and containment, containerization technologies such as Docker are employed, creating secure environments where processes are isolated from each other, preventing potential breaches from spreading. Regular security audits are conducted to identify and eliminate permission creep, ensuring that access and permissions strictly follow the principle of least privilege.

Data Storage

Securing data storage is fundamental to protect sensitive information and ensuring the integrity and availability of the system. However, several vulnerabilities can expose stored data to significant risks. Unencrypted storage leaves data accessible if the medium is compromised, while weak access controls fail to adequately enforce user roles and permissions, increasing the risk of unauthorized access.

To address these vulnerabilities and threats, we implement a multi-layered approach to secure data storage. All data within the framework is stored across different databases. User data is stored in a SQL database, ensuring a clear separation of critical information. Furthermore, user passwords are encrypted with a hash and a salt, providing an additional layer of security. Since SQL databases are not encrypted by default, when rolling out a production deployment of the framework we also need to take care of incorporating an encryption to further protect the stored data. For this we are looking into data encryption using AES-256 or other strong encryption algorithms, ensuring that sensitive information remains protected even if the storage medium is compromised. We enforce strict RBACs to regulate permissions and limit access to authorized users only. In cloud environments, robust storage security measures are implemented, including correct configurations, continuous monitoring, and strong identity management practices. In this context we can rely on already proven solutions and implementations like BeeGFS for HPC systems and Ceph or Lustre for cloud storage solutions managed by Kubernetes.

7.4.2 Kubernetes

Within the DECICE framework, Kubernetes serves as the primary orchestration platform, playing a crucial role in managing operations across the compute continuum. This includes deploying jobs and pods, creating Persistent Volumes (PV) for data storage and access, and managing all communications between components. As a result, securing communication between pods and nodes is extremely important. Furthermore, effective user permission management is essential for maintaining data security, protecting data transfer, and preventing unauthorized access and potential security breaches.

Role-Based Access Control (RBAC)

In Kubernetes, RBAC is a key security control to ensure that cluster users and workloads have only the access to resources required to execute their roles. RBAC defines two types of roles: ClusterRoles and Roles. ClusterRoles are used to grant access to cluster-wide resources, while Roles are used to grant access to resources within a namespace, which provides a mechanism for isolating groups of resources within a single cluster. By defining roles and assigning them to users or service accounts, administrators can restrict access to sensitive resources and ensure that users can only perform

actions that are necessary for their tasks.

In DECICE, RBAC is implemented to manage user permissions and maintain data security. For example, a developer role might be granted read-only access to pods, while an administrator role might be granted full access to manage and update pods. This implementation helps to prevent unauthorized access and potential breaches, aligning with the framework's focus on user permissions, data security and secure data transfer.

Transport Layer Security (TLS)

TLS certifications has an important role in securing communication between components, such as pods, services, and the API server. TLS is a cryptographic protocol that provides end-to-end encryption for data ensuring that data remains confidential. In Kubernetes, TLS certifications are used to authenticate and verify the identity of components, preventing attacks and ensuring that only authorized components can communicate with each other. The API server, etcd, and pod-to-pod communication are all secured using TLS certifications.

TLS certifications are essential for maintaining the security and integrity of the hybrid compute plane in DECICE. By using TLS certifications, DECICE ensures that all communication between pods and nodes is encrypted and authenticated, preventing unauthorized access and data breaches. This is particularly important for DECICE, as it handles sensitive data and requires a high level of security to protect it.

Hierarchical Namespaces

Hierarchical Namespaces is a feature that allows administrators to organize and manage resources in a hierarchical structure. This feature enables the creation of nested namespaces, where a parent namespace can contain multiple child namespaces. Each namespace can have its own set of resources, such as pods, services, and deployments, and can be managed independently. Hierarchical Namespaces provides a flexible and scalable way to manage complex environments, making it easier to organize and secure resources. This feature is particularly useful in multitenant environments, where multiple organizations or departments share the same Kubernetes cluster.

In DECICE, Hierarchical Namespaces provides a powerful way to manage security and access control across the compute continuum. One of the key advantages of Hierarchical Namespaces is that security rules, such as RBAC policies, can be applied from the parent namespace to child namespaces, ensuring that access controls are consistently enforced across the entire namespace hierarchy. This means that administrators can define a set of security policies at the parent namespace level, and have them automatically applied to all child namespaces, reducing the administrative workload and ensuring that security is consistently enforced. Additionally, Hierarchical Namespaces allows DECICE to take advantage of inheritance, where child namespaces can inherit resources and policies from their parent namespace, making it easier to manage and scale the environment.

7.5 Deployment and Interoperability

During the development of the DECICE framework, a microservice architecture was adopted, enabling developers to create services and components independently. These developed services are then containerized and prepared for deployment on Kubernetes, taking advantage of the platform's built-in scalability and management capabilities. However, manual container deployment is highly inefficient. To address this challenge, the DECICE framework utilizes Helm charts¹⁰, generating template files that facilitate easy deployments on Kubernetes while enabling effortless application version tracking. Additionally, the framework is integrated with GitLab CI/CD pipelines, ensuring a smooth development-to-production workflow and improving overall administration efficiency.

The DECICE framework is designed with interoperability at its core, achieved through specialized components that bridge diverse services, compute planes, and platforms. For example, the PromQL-to-JSON Wrapper connects to external Prometheus instances, pulling metrics without requiring a new Prometheus server installation, thus leveraging existing monitoring infrastructures. Moreover, a dedicated Grafana Helm chart is included for easy deployment and customized dashboard creation for administrators and users. The PSGC further ensures effective communication between the CM and Kubernetes-deployed compute planes, enabling seamless job submissions, resource allocation, command execution, and data uploads by effectively overcoming architectural, implementation, and technological differences.

7.6 Planned Advancements

Although the final architecture of the DECICE framework has been completed, there are still several key components that need to be integrated and refined to ensure smooth functionality.

Firstly, a user-friendly web frontend will be implemented to provide a graphical interface for end-users to interact with the framework. This web frontend will leverage the external-facing APIs offered by the DECICE Control Manager, enabling users to submit jobs, view job status, retrieve metrics, and log in. This integration will be particularly beneficial for less experienced users, who will be able to navigate the system backed by a graphical user interface.

Secondly, a comprehensive Software Development Kit (SDK) will be developed to facilitate the creation of DECICE API clients. By providing libraries and tools, the SDK will enable other developers and organizations to build their own applications and integrate them with DECICE, thereby expanding the framework's capabilities and ecosystem.

Thirdly, the Snakemake¹¹ workflow management system will be integrated. It is a tool for creating reproducible and scalable data analyses. Workflows are defined using an easy-to-read, adaptable, yet powerful specification language built on top of Python. The main purpose of integrating Snakemake is to enable users to express complex logic in a human-readable and self-contained way, and to scale their workflows on Kubernetes easily.

Lastly, the data upload mechanism will undergo improvements to prevent potential overloads on the DECICE Control Manager and ensure secure data flow within the framework. This optimization will

¹⁰Helm - <https://helm.sh/>

¹¹Snakemake - <https://snakemake.github.io/>

be crucial in maintaining the system's performance and reliability.

In addition to these enhancements, the framework will undergo iterative optimization and refinement without altering its overall architecture until the project's completion. This ongoing improvement process will ensure that the framework remains efficient, scalable, and adaptable to evolving requirements.

8 Summary

This deliverable presented a comprehensive overview of the finalized architecture and interfaces of the DECICE framework. Significant architectural refinements have been made since the previous deliverable, including the unification of the Control Manager for both the Virtual Training Environment and the Production Environment. This unification enhances development speed, scalability, and security, allowing changes to be reflected automatically across both environments.

We detailed the system architecture, highlighting key components such as the Control Manager, Platform Specific Glue Code, Compute Continuum, Digital Twin, Scheduler Controller, Metric Storage, PromQL-to-JSON Wrapper, and Integrated AI Scheduler. Each component's functionality and interactions were explained to provide a clear understanding of the framework's operations.

The API specifications and documentation were outlined, emphasizing the use of OpenAPI for comprehensive documentation and the implementation of RESTful services using HTTP protocols. Security measures were discussed in depth, focusing on data transfer, data processing, and data storage. Implementations include OAuth2 authentication, HTTPS, Role-Based Access Control, and best practices like input validation and the principle of least privilege to ensure the framework's trustworthiness and compliance with relevant security frameworks.

Deployment strategies were presented, highlighting the use of containerization, Helm charts, and GitLab CI/CD pipelines for efficient deployment and management of the framework. The interoperability of the DECICE framework with external services like Prometheus and Grafana was also addressed, showcasing seamless integration capabilities.

While the architecture has been finalized, the deliverable acknowledges challenges encountered and outlines future enhancements. These include the development of a user-friendly web frontend to improve accessibility for end-users, a comprehensive Software Development Kit (SDK) to facilitate the creation of DECICE API clients, the Snakemake integration and improvements to the data upload mechanism to prevent potential overloads and ensure secure data flow.

A Appendix

A.1 Control Manager

A.1.1 Routes

DECICE Control Manager 0.1 OAS 3.1

/openapi.json

DECICE Control Manager OpenAPI specification.

Authorize

auth

POST	/v1/token	Get access token	⌵
POST	/v1/register	Register a new user	⌵

user

GET	/v1/user/me/	Get current user	🔒 ⌵
PATCH	/v1/user/me/	Update current user	🔒 ⌵
GET	/v1/user/	Get all users	🔒 ⌵
PATCH	/v1/user/{id}	Update user	🔒 ⌵
DELETE	/v1/user/{id}	Delete user by ID	🔒 ⌵

submit

GET	/v1/submit/finished	Get previous jobs	🔒 ⌵
POST	/v1/submit/	Create a job	🔒 ⌵
GET	/v1/submit/active	Get active jobs	🔒 ⌵

telemetry

GET	/v1/promql	Get Query	⌵
GET	/v1/hardware-cpu-cores	Get Cpu Cores	⌵
GET	/v1/hardware-memory	Get Memory In Mb	⌵
GET	/v1/memory-utilization	Get Memory Utilization	⌵
GET	/v1/cpu-utilization	Get Cpu Utilization	⌵
GET	/v1/total-pod-number	Get Pod Number In Cluster	⌵
GET	/v1/pod-number	Get Pod Number In Node	⌵
GET	/v1/pv-number	Get Pv Number In Sc	⌵
GET	/v1/free-diskspace	Get Free Root Space In Mb	⌵

command ^

GET /v1/command Get command

trigger ^

POST /v1/schedule/schedule Request Scheduling

default ^

GET /health Health check

A.1.2 Route Specification - Example

POST /v1/register Register a new user

Register a new user

Parameters Cancel

No parameters

Request body *required* application/json

```
{
  "username": "string",
  "email": "user@example.com",
  "full_name": "string",
  "password": "string"
}
```

Execute

Responses

Code	Description	Links
201	Successful Response	No links
Media type: application/json		
Controls Accept header		
Example Value Schema		
<pre>{ "username": "string", "email": "user@example.com", "full_name": "string", "active": false }</pre>		
422	Validation Error	No links
Media type: application/json		
Example Value Schema		
<pre>{ "detail": [{ "loc": ["string", 0], "msg": "string", "type": "string" }] }</pre>		

A.1.3 Schemas

Job > Expand all object
JobCreate > Expand all object
JobList > Expand all object
Token > Expand all object
UserCreate > Expand all object
UserResponse > Expand all object
UserResponseAndToken > Expand all object
UserUpdate > Expand all object

A.2 PromQL Wrapper

A.2.1 Routes

Prometheus JSON Wrapper OpenAPI specification. 0.1 OAS 3.1

/openapi.json

Prometheus JSON Wrapper OpenAPI specification.

default

GET	/health	Health check	⌵
GET	/pool	Get data from Prometheus	⌵

A.3 PSGC

A.3.1 Routes

Platform Specific Glue Code 0.1 OAS 3.1

/openapi.json

This PSGC has been created for test purposes with very limited features.

default

POST	/command	Return command output	⌵
POST	/psgc/jobs	Get all active jobs	⌵
POST	/psgc/jobs/{job_id}	Get one job	⌵
GET	/psgc/health/	Health check	⌵

A.3.2 Schemas

Schemas	
Body_send_command_output_command_post	Expand all object
HTTPValidationError	Expand all object
UserProjectQuery	Expand all object
ValidationError	Expand all object

A.4 Digital Twin

A.4.1 Routes

FastAPI 0.1.0 OAS 3.1
/openapi.json

default

GET	/api/model_core/	Return Data
POST	/api/model_core/	Receive Data

A.5 Scheduler Controller

A.5.1 Routes

FastAPI 0.1.0 OAS 3.1
/openapi.json

default

POST	/scheduler-controller	Get Data From Digital Twin
GET	/health	Health check

A.6 Scheduler

A.6.1 Routes

Scheduler OpenAPI specification. 0.1 OAS 3.1

[/openapi.json](#)

Scheduler OpenAPI specification.

default

^

POST	/schedule	Schedule	▼
GET	/health	Health check	▼